

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS - AN OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Currently, studies on the internal control system and the effectiveness of the internal control system (ICS) are being studied extensively in the world as well as in Vietnam. By reviewing foreign and domestic studies on the effectiveness of SRB, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), the article aims to identify research gaps on the effectiveness of ICS in SMEs and propose some future research directions.

Keywords: Internal control system (ICS), effectiveness of internal control students, small and medium enterprises

1. MAIN PROBLEM

Since the beginning of market opening in the late 1980s, Vietnam's economy has made great strides, welcoming domestic and foreign investment flows, expanding investment forms and ownership forms to build a comprehensive market economy in the direction of Socialism. It is this flexibility in the economy that has created a great motivation to promote the growth of

various types of businesses, the diversity in the scale of enterprises (enterprises). However, due to the young economy, most enterprises are small and medium-sized, according to statistics of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, by 31/12/2021, up to 98% of enterprises are small and medium enterprises (SMEs), these enterprises currently employ a large workforce of the economy and contribute a huge amount to GDP year.

Table 1.

Number of enterprises under 200 employees ¹

Total number of businesses as of 31/12/2021 with revenue	Enterprises with a labor scale of less than 5 people	Enterprises with a labor scale of 5 to 9 people	Enterprises with a labor scale of less than 9 to 50 people	Enterprises with a labor scale of less than 50 to 199 people	Total number of SMEs by size	Ratio of SMEs/Total Enterprises (%)
668.503	340.462	171.179	123.55	23.144	658.335	98.45%

The difficulties that most of these enterprises face are the level of capital use, the level of application of technical technology, the level of enterprise resource management ... and a limitation that cannot be ignored is the limitation in the organization of the accounting information system (ICT), which has not kept up with the increasing requirements for providing accounting information to managers promptly and accurately; In addition, the information is also provided to different users inside and outside the business. Therefore, the organization of an effective accounting information system will be a lever for businesses to create useful information, help managers make quick and accurate decisions, giving businesses a higher competitive advantage in the economy.

When it comes to IT organizations, many businesses and organizers often think of the trend of applying ERP (Enterprise resource planning) in businesses, which is a direction that is considered necessary but requires huge initial investment costs as well as human resources must have certain qualifications to be able to absorb and operate the system ERP system smoothly – this is the biggest challenge for SMEs. So we need to

organize ICT close to the capacity of SMEs, which can develop in the future, which is what SMEs need.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1 General theory of SMEs in the world

In the world, there are many definitions of SMEs that are understood and regulated differently depending on each organization, region or country, but in general, there are currently two basic methods used to define or classify SMEs: qualitative and quantitative criteria:

(1) The group of qualitative criteria is based on basic characteristics of SMEs such as low level of management and expertise, simplicity in administration and management, application of few technologies in operation,... These criteria have the advantage of reflecting the true nature of SMEs, but in practice are often difficult to measure and define specifically, so this group of criteria is often used to survey or as a basis for evaluating the operation of an SME but is rarely used for classification in practice.

1. The group of quantitative criteria is considered an important measure and is often used first to classify SMEs, quantitative measures can be used individually or simultaneously such as: the number of employees

¹ <https://www.gso.gov.vn/px-web-2/?pxid=V0525&theme=Doanh%20nghi%E1%BB%87p>

(can be regular workers, average annual workers or actual workers), The value of equity or assets (can be the total value of assets (capital), revenue or profit (total revenue / year, total value added / year). Because of its easy-to-measure nature, quantitative criteria are often widely used to define and classify SMEs, but in practice quantitative criteria are only relative when there are differences in space and time or industry standards. Therefore, when defining or classifying SMEs according to quantitative criteria, they must be combined with external factors, including: (a) The level of development of a country or region: the higher the level of development of that country or region, the quantitative criteria often increase to match the actual situation. For example, an enterprise with 400 regular employees is not in the SME category in Vietnam but in Germany it is classified as an SME. (b) Nature of industries and fields of operation: due to the characteristics of each industry or field of operation, the number of employees and capital changes, there are industries that own a lot of labor such as textiles and garments,...; have capital-intensive industries such as electricity, information technology,...(3) Territories in the same country or region: due to geographical characteristics, different levels of development in the same country or large region, which may lead to changes in the definition and classification of SMEs.

Meanwhile, large organizations over time also have several different perspectives, depending on the purpose of classifying SMEs to achieve the goals that the organization sets:

1. According to the World Bank, SMEs are divided by size as follows: (1) Microenterprises with fewer than 10 workers and total turnover not exceeding US\$100,000; (2) Small businesses with fewer than 50 employees and no more than \$3 million in total annual revenue; (3) The medium-sized enterprise has a smaller number of employees than 300 and a total annual turnover of not more than 15 million USD.

2. For the purpose of guiding audit performance and emphasizing the properties affecting audit work in SMEs, the International Committee on Auditing and Assurance Services (IAASB) of the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) considers SMEs to have the following characteristics: (1) SME owners are usually one or several individuals; (2) The scope of the enterprise's activities is narrow and deals in only one or certain items, so it cannot dominate the entire commodity market; (3) The organization of accounting work is simple, the accounting apparatus has only a few employees and (4) No attention or very little attention to the internal control system at the enterprise.

1. With the aim of building a system of accounting standards to create harmony between accounting standards of a country and international accounting standards and standardize the quality of information on financial statements, ensuring the interests of information users in making investment decisions with the

goal of targeting user characteristics Information on the financial statements, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) defines SMEs as enterprises with the following constituent elements: (1) Not or have not participated in listing on the stock market and their business activities do not have a strong impact on the economy and (2) General financial statements must be disclosed to users outside the company. Non-company users include: owners that are not involved in the management of the business, current creditors, potential creditors and financial authorities.

2.1 General theory of SMEs in Vietnam

In Vietnam, from 1998 onwards, there has been no document regulating the classification of enterprises by size, but mainly classifies enterprises into 2 groups: state-owned enterprises and non-state enterprises. In particular, the Union Ministry of Finance – Social War Invalids has Circular No. 21/LĐTT dated 17/06/1993 stipulating: a small enterprise is an enterprise with less than two of the following three criteria: having a legal capital of less than one billion VND, having a number of employees of less than 100 people, having a total annual turnover of less than 10 billion VND. This determination aims to have investment and management policy.

The introduction of the Government's Official Letter No. 681/1998/CP-KTN, dated 20/06/1998 on strategic orientation and policies to support SME development marked the beginning of the process of unifying the concept and promoting support for SMEs in Vietnam. Official Letter No. 681 stipulates that SMEs are enterprises with business capital of less than VND 5 billion and the average number of employees is less than 200 people per year. However, this letter affirmed that these criteria are mainly administrative conventions to serve the management and application of development assistance policies.

In line with the new trend, on 23/11/2001 the Government issued Decree No. 90/2001/ND-CP to support SME development. Accordingly, Decree No. 90 has set out the official standard, uniformly applied to classify SMEs. Decree No. 90/2001/ND-CP stipulates that "SMEs are production and business establishments under current law, with registered business capital not exceeding VND 10 billion or having an average annual number of employees not exceeding 300 people",

Then, according to the Government's Decree No. 56/2009/ND-CP dated 30/6/2009, SMEs are business establishments registered for business under the law, divided into three levels: micro, small and medium according to the size of total capital (total capital equivalent to total assets determined in the balance sheet of the enterprise) or the average number of employees per year (total capital source is the priority criterion). For different industries, capital and labor criteria are also different (table 1)

Table 2

Regulations on SME identification according to the Government's Decree No. 56/2009/ND-CP dated 30/6/2009

Field	Scale	Small Business		Medium enterprises	
	Micro enterprises	Total capital	Number of employees	Total capital	Number of employees
I. Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	10 people or less	20 billion or less	From over 10 people to 200 people	From over 20 billion to 100 billion	From over 200 to 300 people
II. Industry and construction	10 people or less	20 billion or less	From over 10 people to 200 people	From over 20 billion to 100 billion	From over 200 to 300 people
III. Trade and services	10 people or less	20 billion or less	From over 10 people to 50 people	From over 20 billion to 100 billion	From over 50 to 100 people

In addition, some professional organizations, financial institutions, business support organizations,... In Vietnam, there have been a number of classifications of SMEs to support their own operations:

1. The Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry (VCCI) bases on two criteria of labor and capital of the industry to classify SMEs with large enterprises to help the chamber of commerce and industry have grounds for capital support, technology consultancy,... for SMEs (table 3):

Table 3

Classification criteria of SMEs of VCCI

Industry	Classification criteria			
	Small Business		Medium enterprises	
	Total capital	Labour	Total capital	Labour
Industry	VND <5 billion	< 200 people	VND 5-10 billion	200-500 people
Trade and services	VND <5 billion	< 50 people	VND 5-10 billion	50-100 people

Up to now, the SME Support Law (National Assembly, 2017) was passed by the National Assembly on June 12, 2017 and officially took effect from January 1, 2018 and applied until now, the Law clearly stipulates that: "SMEs including micro-enterprises, small enterprises and medium-sized enterprises, have an average number of employees participating in social insurance not exceeding 200 people and meet one of two criteria The following lice:

- Total capital not exceeding VND 100 billion
- Total adjacent revenue not exceeding VND 300 billion

In order to make SME support more substantial, the Government continues to issue Decree 39/2018/ND-CP (Government, 2018), dated March 11, 2018, detailing a number of articles of the SME Support Law and Decree 39/2019/ND-CP (Government, 2019), dated May 10, 2019 on the organization and operation of the SME Development Fund.

Thus, in Vietnam, the development of the theoretical basis for SMEs is implemented very clearly and methodically, this is an important basis for SMEs to be supported and developed stronger in the future, meeting the requirements of the development of the market economy and international integration as well as overcoming new difficulties like epidemics, instability of the world economy.

2.3 Theory of Internal Control System (ICS):

According to COSO (COSO, 2012, 2016) internal control is a process influenced by management, regulators, and other individuals, designed to provide reasonable assurance of operational, reporting and compliance objectives.

According to the Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Sector Internal Auditing Standards (INTOSAI, 2016) of the International Organization of Supreme Audit Bodies (INTOSAI), because Internal Control is an integral process undertaken by a management and personnel entity and designed to address risks and reasonably ensure that to pursue Physical tasks, the following general objectives are being achieved: (1) Orderly, ethical, economic, efficient and efficient implementation; (2) fulfillment of liability obligations; (3) comply with applicable laws and regulations; (4) protect resources against loss, abuse, and damage. This framework is based on COSO 2004, so it has many similarities with COSO 2004.

According to the International Federation of Accountants (ISA, 2009), internal control is an integral part of an organization's governance system and risk management capabilities, which are understood, impacted, and actively monitored by regulators, regulators, and other employees to take advantage of opportunities and counter threats to achieve objectives of the organization

In Vietnam, internal control is presented in Auditing Standard No. 315 (Ministry of Finance, 2014) as follows: "A process designed, implemented and maintained by management, management and other individuals in the entity to create reasonable assurance of the entity's ability to achieve its objectives in ensuring the reliability of the report financial statements, ensuring efficiency, operational performance, compliance with relevant laws and regulations". Highly similar to ISA 315.

According to the Law on Accounting (National Assembly, 2015), internal control is the establishment

and organization of internal implementation of mechanisms, policies, processes and internal regulations in accordance with the provisions of law to ensure prevention, timely detection and handling of risks and achievement of set requirements.

3. FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS IN SMES

3.1 Worldwide

In China, the topic of study of internal control systems is studied quite a lot:

- Studies by Jiang & Li (2010), using deterministic research methodology, show that the special role of the control environment, risk warning, poor communication of management information and ineffective control activities has led to the effectiveness of the internal control system.

- Xiao (2011) studies using questionnaires and descriptive statistical tools to show that in SMEs, the external environment, business linkages, good financial management will positively affect the effectiveness of SMEs, in addition, corporate culture, decentralization of positions and quality of the Supervisory Board does not affect the effectiveness of the ICS.

- Wang et al., (2019) investigated the causal relationship of the effectiveness of the internal control system on the development of SMEs listed on the Chinese stock exchange. The study shows that, in particular, the

controlling role of large shareholders affects the effectiveness of internal controls in risk control, thereby affecting the sustainable growth of SMEs.

- Along with the trend of sustainable development, a study by Ma et al., (2022) has shown the important role of ICS in applying environmental-social-corporate governance (ESG) tools. The study gathered data from companies listed on Chinese stock exchanges from 2014 to 2019, using a linear regression model to show a close relationship between internal controls, including environmental investments, that have a positive impact on environmental security in both direct and indirect ways. Although this research does not go directly to SMEs, it is also a development direction that is considered the current trend of most businesses, especially those that use and impact on the environment (polluting activities, resource use ...)

In other countries, the study of SRH and its role has been studied very early and there have been many studies showing factors affecting the effectiveness of SRH as well as the role of SRH in SME activities, including the following studies:

- Hidayah & Putra (2013) Using statistical methods described by interviewing SME owners (58 Muslim enterprises), the study identified 3 problems of SMEs: Lack of management skills due to lack of competence and lack of supervision; lack of application of information technology to manage, these are the 2 biggest issues affecting the effectiveness of ICS; 3rd, facing the need to grow the scale of the business.

Summary table of foreign studies on SRH at SMEs

Author	Year	Country	Method	Result
Jiang & Li	2010	China	Qualitative	Control environment, risk assessment, monitoring and negative impact control activities
Xiao	2011	China	Descriptive statistics	The external environment, corporate affiliation, financial control activities have a positive impact. Controlled, decentralized, non-impact training environment
Wang et al.	2019	China	Linear structure	The role of major shareholders impacts risk control of ICS positively impacting sustainable development
Ma et al.	2022	China	Regression	Green environmental investment has a direct and indirect impact on the effectiveness of green environmental protection, thereby positively impacting on green innovation;
Hidayah & Son	2013	Islam	Descriptive statistics	Poor management skills, poor application of information technology, development pressure negatively affect the effectiveness of the ICT

3.2. In Vietnam:

As part of the theoretical basis of SMEs, in Vietnam before 1998, the concept of SMEs was not formed, until 1998 there was a legal document mentioning the classification of enterprises by scale (Official Letter No. 681/1998/CP-KTN, dated 20/06/1998 of the Government), from which the study on SMEs appeared in the study on SMEs, Spanning from 2000 to 2016, the studies were few, focusing on state-owned enterprises and general enterprises in Vietnam, not on SMEs such as: Pham Thanh Hai (Hải, 2001) researched on cooperatives at Vietnamese cement enterprises; Pham Quang Trung (Trung, 2000) researched the role of ICS in management information; Tran Viet Lam (Lâm, 2014) researched the internal control system in

state-owned enterprises; Nguyen Hong Anh and Nguyen Thi Ngoc Lan (Anh & Lan, 2019) researched on cooperatives at seafood enterprises, ... The general characteristics of these studies using qualitative research or descriptive statistics, the purpose is to only learn about economic cooperatives in enterprises by sectors and economic sectors, but not to delve into the assessment of cooperative systems at the scale of enterprises, especially SMEs.

Recently, some authors have measured the impact of factors affecting the effectiveness of CSR such as:

- Nguyen Van Thang (Thắng, 2019) conducted a survey of directors, human resource managers, internal control department managers at more than 800 enterprises in Vietnam to assess whether the role of CSR

components has impact on compliance risks. The author uses descriptive statistics and linear regression models to process the survey results. The results indicate that the Environment of Control, Information and Communication, and Monitoring components have an impact on reducing compliance risks. Through research, it has been shown that the important role of ICS for enterprises is aimed at complying with legal documents of State management agencies.

- Ha Xuan Thach and Nguyen Thi Mai Sang (Thach & Sang, 2019) this is an elaborate and complete study when reviewing the impact of factors of the internal control system on the effectiveness of the internal control system and the relationship to the performance of enterprises, The study has synthesized many domestic and foreign works. As a result, the author built an impact model between variables consisting of 6 hypotheses and used the proposed linear structure method (PLS-SEM) to measure the degree of impact.

Regarding research works on the effectiveness of CSB, there are very few studies in Vietnam, the number

of studies found on the basis of national research has only 2 published works, specifically as follows:

- Do Thi Huyen and Nguyen Thi Dieu Thu (Huyền & Thu, 2016) conducted a study on the effectiveness of the effectiveness of ICS in SMEs, in the study using qualitative research methods, emphasizing that risk management mentioned in CSR is an important basis for an indispensable component of CSR from which to make recommendations including: See risk management as a priority, assess risk, and ultimately develop an action plan.

- Pham Quoc Thuan, Nguyen Cao Cuong (Thuần & Cường, 2020) carried out an in-depth study to evaluate the effectiveness of ICS in SMEs in Vietnam, the study is still based on the COSO 2013 framework. The two authors used an overview of many previous studies and developed a survey, a 5-level linkert scale, the survey subjects are accountants at SMEs in Ho Chi Minh City, but the study only stops at the level of analyzing EFA discovery factors from which to give policy implications that have not been assessed the degree of impact of factors on the effectiveness of ICS.

Table 4

Synthesis of domestic research on the effectiveness of ICS at SMEs

Author	Year	Country	Method	Result
Pham Thanh Hai	2001	Vietnam	Qualitative	Recommendations on the construction of ICS
Pham Quang Trung	2000	Vietnam	Qualitative	Recommendations on the role of ICS in management information
Tran Viet Lam	2014	Vietnam	Qualitative	Environmental Factors Control, Risk Assessment, Information and Communication, Monitoring, Monitoring and Corrective Actions Have an Impact on Increasing the Effectiveness of CSR
Nguyen Hong Anh, Nguyen Thi Ngoc Lan	2019	Vietnam	Qualitative	Environmental Control Factors, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, Information and Communication, Monitoring have an impact on increasing the efficiency of environmental protection along with the characteristics of seafood enterprises
Nguyen Van Thang	2019	Vietnam	Multivariate regression	Controlling, information and communication, and monitoring environments have adverse effects (-) compliance risks
Ha Xuan Thach, Nguyen Thi Mai Sang	2019	Vietnam	Qualitative	Develop impact models Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, Information and Communication, Monitoring impacts on the effectiveness of CSS and impacts on Operational Efficiency
Do Thi Huyen, Do Thi Dieu Thu	2016	Vietnam	Qualitative	Proposal to build risk management mechanism in ICS
Pham Quoc Thuan, Nguyen Cao Cuong	2020	Vietnam	Survey, EFA	Evaluate the effectiveness of CSR through the average score of each factor.

4. CONCLUSION AND RESEARCH ORIENTATION:

In the process of reviewing foreign and domestic research, it can be clearly seen that the outstanding research trend on SRH in general and SRH in SMEs in particular, especially the study on the effectiveness of CSR based on the COSO model (COSO, 2013) selected

by many authors and research groups. The authors and research team can study from the factors affecting the effectiveness of the IPR, then expand the studies when studying the impact of the OSH on other aspects of the business such as operational efficiency, management information, and enterprise risk. Summing up the research, we can see the following trends:

Figure 1: Synthesis of research directions on CSR in SMEs

Especially, when researching foreign studies, it is easy to see that developing countries will concentrate a lot of research on SMEs, this is one of the business groups accounting for a very high proportion of the total number of operating enterprises, similar to Vietnam. However, in Vietnam, research on SRH in SMEs is very limited, it must be said that publications are very few, this is also the research gap that authors and research groups can target. The proposed research directions may be as follows:

- Study the impact of component factors of the ICS on the effectiveness of the ICS, the component factors can be built based on the COSO or COBIT template.

- Study non-component factors affecting the effectiveness of the ICS, these factors may be factors outside the unit (competition, legal environment, business risks,...) or inside the unit (information technology application, scale, etc capital structure, ...)

- Study the impact of the CSR on the operational aspects of the business. These operational aspects are very extensive, such as: operational efficiency (financial efficiency, management efficiency, personnel efficiency, capital use efficiency,...), competitiveness (revenue, market share, customers, ...), quality of management information (accounting information, usefulness of information, ...) ...

The study of SRH is increasingly interested by researchers, especially in the increasingly complex economic, social and political environment, building an effective CSR is extremely important, especially for SMEs, the most vulnerable business group in the economy but a shoulder business group It's extremely important in any economy. Through this research review, the author expects more research to contribute more effectively to the management, efficiency and efficiency for businesses in general and SMEs in particular.

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